

SPORTS TOURISM AND ITS STRATEGIC DEVELOPMENT WAYS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *Sports tourism is one of the promising areas of development of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan, contributing to the development of the economy, improving the country's image, and popularizing a healthy lifestyle. This article considers the current state of sports tourism in Uzbekistan, its potential, and strategic ways of development. Particular attention is paid to infrastructure, cultural and natural resources, and government and private sector initiatives. The country has significant potential to attract outdoor enthusiasts because of its unique geographical location, rich cultural heritage, and diverse natural landscapes. The article discusses the current state of sports tourism in Uzbekistan, its main directions, as well as strategic ways of development. Statistical data are given, problems are analyzed, and recommendations improve the country's competitiveness in the international tourism market.*

Keywords: *popularization of a healthy lifestyle, sports tourism, cultural heritage, active recreation.*

Introduction

Today, every country possesses real opportunities to support tourism through the attraction of both public and private investments, including investments in infrastructure, introduction of innovations and new business models, support for local communities, and for micro, small, and medium-sized businesses as the cornerstone of economic development. President Mr. Shavkat Mirziyoyev has designated tourism as a strategic sector of the national economy. Uzbekistan, historically at the crossroads of civilizations, boasts impressive historical, archaeological, and cultural resources that hold significant value for international tourism. Within the country's borders, more than 8,000 historical and natural landmarks can be found, many of which are included in UNESCO's lists of tangible and intangible cultural heritage. Today, Uzbekistan is an open country to the world, offering visa-free entry to citizens of 95 nations. By comparison, in 2017, residents of only nine countries could visit Uzbekistan without an entry visa. In a short period, because of the consistent policies pursued by the leadership and government, along with active promotion programs, an unprecedented growth in the number of foreign tourists visiting our country has been observed. While in 2017, Uzbekistan received 2.7 million tourists, in 2019, this

figure reached 6.7 million. It is expected that by the end of 2023, this number will reach approximately 7.2 million, surpassing the pre-pandemic level by 7%.

This article considers the development of sports tourism in Uzbekistan and identifies strategic directions for strengthening this sector. Particular attention is paid to the analysis of the current state of sports tourism, its potential, and problems, as well as proposals for the development of national resources to attract tourists interested in sports tourism. Sports tourism in Uzbekistan encompasses a variety of outdoor activities, including mountain hiking, water sports, cycling, rock climbing, mountaineering, and others. Significant attention is paid to the development of infrastructure and support for sporting events to attract both local and international tourists.

Uzbekistan is developing a Tourism Development Strategy until 2040, aiming to attract 20 million foreign tourists and 30 million domestic tourists annually, increasing tourism's share of GDP to 7%. The strategy focuses on creating a modern, accessible, and traveler-friendly ecosystem by 2040, including developing new tourist routes, global marketing campaigns, and investment packages for key areas. Sports tourism is a type of sport that aims to improve human athletic performance in overcoming natural obstacles. Sportiness of tourism consists in overcoming natural obstacles, in the application of various tactics and techniques of overcoming obstacles. Sports tourism, first, sports hiking, is a team sport, in which the traditions of mutual help and mutual assistance, sports discipline, self-improvement, and mutual transfer of knowledge and experience are strong.

Uzbekistan expanded its tourism infrastructure to meet the growing demand. With 124 new hotels (6,400 additional beds) and 239 new hostels (7,600 additional beds), the total number of accommodations exceeds 6,100, providing more than 161,000 beds. The introduction of renowned hotel brands, including Azimut, Bentley, Bill Wyndham & Co in Tashkent, along with new properties such as Hilton Garden Inn Termez Airitom, Dedeman Hotel in Navoi, Hilton Samarkand Regency, Hilton Garden Inn Samarkand Sogd, and Intercontinental.

The number of nationwide travel agencies increased to 3,686 with the establishment of 866 new agencies. The training of 700 new certified guides, bringing the national total to 3,200 licensed tour guides. [1] Sport tourism lets you get acquainted with the culture and life of different countries and peoples, with wonderful and often even unique corners of nature, interesting sights, glee from communication, and make reliable comrades.

Participation in sports hikes of the initial categories of complexity and in competitions of distances does not require significant financial costs, and simultaneously allows you to get the basic skills and enjoyment of participation in hikes and competitions. Sports tourism, as a complex sport performed in a complex natural and social environment, requires from the athlete versatile knowledge, skills, experience, and preparation.

The total global market of active and extreme tourism is estimated by different experts at about \$400-500 billion. In 2024, one of the international tourist publications named Brazil, the best country for extreme tourism. Greece, Costa Rica, Argentina, and Portugal are also among the leaders of the rating. The key categories by which the countries were evaluated were resources for extreme tourism, safety, natural resources, infrastructure, cultural resources, image, and brand of extreme tourism, as well as government policies to support development.[15]

In several countries, tourism plays an important role in generating gross domestic product, activating the external economic balance, creating new jobs, and providing employment. It has a significant impact on such key sectors of the economy as transport and communications,

construction, agriculture, production of consumer goods, and others, serving as a kind of stabilizer of socio-economic growth.

Methodology

According to international experts, Uzbekistan has excellent opportunities for year-round tourist services because of its location near the 40th parallel, which is considered an ecological optimum on the plain. This important geographical landmark passes through the famous city of Samarkand. In addition, the country's mountainous terrain occupies 21% of the total area, where the diverse natural zones of low, medium, and high mountains create ideal conditions for the development of mountain and eco-tourism. These favorable natural conditions contribute to the active promotion of ecotourism, which in international practice is considered an innovative direction.[5]

Ecotourism is focused on active recreation and offers travelers a unique opportunity to enjoy the diversity of nature, enriching their ecological knowledge. For the organizers, this type of tourism brings significant revenues. The peculiarity of Uzbekistan lies in its rich landscapes, which contribute to the development of ecotourism and support the harmony of man with the environment. Travelers are drawn to the unique natural formations—bizarre cliffs, deep gorges, ancient caves, spectacular waterfalls, and pure, healing springs—which provide ideal conditions for recreation and adventure in this amazing natural setting. The active development of infrastructure and services in this area will not only help to increase the tourist flow but also to preserve the country's natural heritage.

To make the most complete classification of modern types of tourism, it is important to consider the key characteristics that define each of them. These include the nationality of tourism, the main need that is satisfied by a tourist trip; the means of travel; the type of accommodation; the duration of the trip; the composition of the group; organizational forms; the basic principles of price formation for tourism products, and so on.

The choice of a tourist destination is determined by several factors, including location (natural and man-made features, cultural elements), event (festival, sports competitions), available opportunities for activities (sports activities, medical services), and the state of the material base, as well as transportation infrastructure. It is important to consider the tourist's level of readiness, as well as the information he/she has received from educational, popular, and other sources, including mass media. The choice of destination depends on the assessment of available ways to entertain and satisfy the needs of tourists.

In October 2020, Uzbek President Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a decree on the development of mass sports in the republic. The document stipulates that 104 billion sums (\$10 million) will be allocated annually from the state budget for programs to develop running, mini-football, cycling, badminton, streetball, and Workout (street fitness). 1.4 trillion sums (\$133 million) will be allocated to the program for the construction of pedestrian and bicycle paths [15]

Results and discussion

Nowadays, there is only one modern ski resort in the republic. Amirsoy Mountain Resort is located 65 km from the capital of Uzbekistan, on the spurs of the Chatkal range of the western part of the Tien Shan Mountains. Amirsoy is the first all-season mountain resort in the country, built according to world standards. In December 2019, the first phase of the 892-hectare complex was completed, a project finished in less than two years. The resort was designed and built by specialists from Italy, Germany, Austria, Austria, Argentina, Spain, and Denmark. The \$100 mln

project was realized by the Andorran company PGI Management. Now, preparations are underway for the construction of the second stage of the resort.[14]

Another all-season tourist complex with ski slopes has been built in the Zaamin district of the Jizzak region. The cost of the project is \$300 million. Turkish business is going to take part in the resort's construction in one of the most picturesque places of the republic. Now the infrastructure - roads and communications - is being brought to the object. Austrian company Doppelmayr has built here two cable cars of gondola-chair type and three elevators. In today's world, a wide variety of amateur sports clubs and sections cater to individuals looking to perfect their skills in skiing, watersports, and equestrian tourism. There is also a suitable infrastructure in our country. All this equally contributes to the development of sports tourism. [13]

The Federation of Extreme and Mountain Tourism, a non-governmental, non-profit organization established in 2007, is engaged in the development of this tourist area in Uzbekistan. The main activities of the Federation are such types of tourism and sports as sports tourism, orienteering, MTB (mountain biking), BMX biking, mountain and ecological tourism, local history tourism, auto, and motorcycle tourism, bicycle tourism, water tourism, speleotourism (visiting caves), paragliding, rock climbing and urban sports.[6]

An international tourism festival on active tourism was held in the Samarkand region. As for sports tourism, it is precisely a type of sport aimed at improving a person in overcoming obstacles and applying various tactics and techniques. Now, the infrastructure necessary for a major international tournament is being created in the republic - a project for the construction of an Olympic town on an area of 160 hectares has already been developed. On the Chirchik River, where rowing competitions will be held, 5 km of embankment will be improved and a park of 270 hectares will be developed along the rowing channel[.]

The Uzbek authorities rely on the development of sports infrastructure and the attraction of active tourists to the republic. Uzbekistan's natural and geographical location and climatic conditions create ideal prerequisites for outdoor sports all year round. Today, the new sports history of the country is being written not only by professional athletes but also by ordinary people who choose sports tourism in Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan has unique natural resources, diverse natural landscapes, and rich cultural heritage, historical heritage, and cultural wealth, which contribute to the development of sports tourism. Uzbekistan has unique natural resources that contribute to the development of sports tourism. Among the key regions are:

- Mountainous areas: Chingan, Beldersay, Nuratau, and Fan Mountains, which are popular with mountaineers and hikers.
- Water resources: Chatkal and Ugam rivers, suitable for rafting and kayaking.
- Deserts: Kyzylkum, where jeep safaris and camel treks are developing.

The State Committee released tourism statistics for 2022, according to which more than 5 million tourists visited Uzbekistan. This is 2.8 times more than in 2021 post-pandemic year.

Most often Uzbekistan is visited by citizens of Kazakhstan - over 1.5 million people. 1.4 million tourists from Tajikistan also vacation here. In the fourth place is Russia, and as predicted by all analysts of the tourism industry, the inflow of Russians to Uzbekistan has increased several times: 190,500 Russians visited Uzbekistan in 2021 compared to 567,700 this year. This is an almost threefold increase.[12]

Uzbekistan is currently working actively to improve its tourism infrastructure, including the construction of sports complexes and the modernization of the transport network. Insufficient information on tourist routes and a dearth of qualified sports tourism specialists plague the industry.

Figure 1. The growth of both expenditures and receipts in international tourism.

The dataset reflects the overall pattern of growth in expenditure and receipts in Uzbekistan's international tourism sector from the mid-1990s to 2020, with a marked increase in tourism receipts and expenditure in current U.S. dollars from 2007 to 2010. The peak of travel expenditures was in 2008. After a sharp increase in the share of international tourism expenditure in total imports between 2011 and 2015, there is a stable trend from 2016 onwards. This stable share indicates a more balanced contribution of tourism expenditure to the total value of imports. GDP and GDP per capita experienced consistent growth from the mid-1990s until 2019, with positive average annual growth rates throughout this period. The growth is indicative of general economic development, which complements the growth in tourism activity, with fluctuations in some years. [2]

Figure 2. Increases in expenditures and receipts in the international tourism sector

Uzbekistan's GDP growth appears to have been steady from the late 1990s to 2010, showing high percentages of annual growth, peaking in 2010, showing economic resilience despite global shocks such as the financial crisis, before declining from the mid-2010s onwards.

Tourism-related data show significant growth in both outbound and inbound numbers from the late 1990s through the 2000s, reaching a notable peak in the late 2010s, followed by a potential decline, indicating a mature but volatile tourism market that may be affecting GDP [3]

Figure 3. GDP per capita growth from 1995 to 2023

GDP per capita in Uzbekistan had variable growth between 1995 and 2023, with notable fluctuations after 2005, peaking in 2007 with a growth of 7.9%. This shows a period of strong economic growth in these years, followed by more moderate growth. Annual GDP growth has been positive since 1995, recovering quickly from the initial downturn, and the strong performance in 2007-2008 was likely because of economic reforms or foreign trade factors. Growth slowed again in 2009 and 2016, correlating with the global economic downturn. Current GDP in U.S. dollars has shown a consistent growth trajectory, increasing from about 13 billion in 1995 to over 101 billion by 2023, reflecting Uzbekistan’s overall economic [4]. The economic growth of Uzbekistan has been impressive in recent years. The current GDP in US dollars shows a constant growth trajectory, increasing from about 13 billion in 1995 to over 101 billion by 2023. This growth reflects not only the general economic development of the country but also opens up new horizons for various industries, including sports tourism.

The development of tourist destinations in Uzbekistan is an important strategy to attract tourists and diversify the tourism offer. Uzbekistan has a rich historical and cultural heritage that can be attributed to various tourist destinations. There are several key aspects that can be considered when developing tourist destinations in Uzbekistan to the brand level: historical cities, natural attractions, cultural events, and festivals, gastronomic and hiking in deserts and mountains, and rural tourism.

Uzbekistan is known for such historical cities as Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva. These cities have a rich history, architecture, and monuments attractive to tourists. Developing itineraries covering these cities and their attractions will allow tourists to experience the unique culture and history of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan also offers many natural attractions that can be included in tourist itineraries. For example, Lake Aidarkul, the Tien Shan Mountains and the Kyzylkum Desert offer tourists opportunities such as trekking, mountaineering, jeep safaris and ecotourism [5]

Uzbekistan offers many areas for sports tourism, each of which has its unique potential and opportunities for development:

- **Mountain tourism:** In the regions, Chimgan, and Beldersai can engage in mountaineering and walking. These places are famous for their picturesque landscapes and high mountains, which make them ideal for outdoor activities. The development potential in this direction is high, thanks to the growing interest in ecotourism and active types of rest.
- **Water tourism:** River Chatkal and Ugam offer excellent opportunities for rafting and kayaking. This direction has average potential, but with an increase in investment in infrastructure, such as recreation databases and equipment rental, it can attract more tourists.

▪ Desert tourism: Traveling in the Kyzylkum desert with a Safari on camels provides a unique experience. This direction also has an average potential, but with the right investment, you can create unforgettable adventures for tourists.

▪ Bicycle tourism: The Fergana Valley offers many bicycle routes suitable for both beginners and experienced cyclists. The high development potential in this direction is because of the growing interest in active rest and ecology.

Every year, Uzbekistan improves its infrastructure and investment in sports facilities, which creates favorable conditions for the development of sports tourism.

Table 1: Main directions of sports tourism in Uzbekistan [6]

Direction	regions	Types of activity	Development potential
Mountain tourism	Chingan, Beldersay	Mountaineering, hiking	high
Water tourism	Chatkal rivers, Ugam	rafting, kayaking	medium
Desert tourism	Kyzylkum safari	camel trekking	medium
Bicycle tourism	Fergana Valley	bicycle routes	high

The table 1 shows the main directions of sports tourism in Uzbekistan, where the potential for development is high in mountain tourism and bicycle tourism. Also, the table shows that such sports as rafting and kayaking are also developing.

Based on the analyses made, the following strategic development paths are suggested:

✓ Infrastructure improvement: Development of hotel services, transport routes, and sports facilities, modernization of hotel facilities, creation of sports complexes and training centers.

✓ Training of specialists: Training of personnel in sports tourism and organization of events.

✓ Promotion: Active promotion of sports tourism in international markets through participation in exhibitions, forums, and specialized events.

✓ Marketing and advertising: Creation of information resources and advertising campaigns to attract tourists.

✓ Cooperation with international organizations: Participation in international tourism exhibitions and forums.

✓ Development of new routes: Creation of unique tourist routes based on local traditions and culture.

✓ Training and certification: Training and certification.

✓ Training and certification: Training of personnel in sports tourism, promotion of professional development, and certification of services.

Sports tourism (ST) is a unique combination of sport and travel, where the main goal is to improve sports skills while overcoming natural obstacles. It is not just a walk in nature, but an active activity that requires special training and knowledge.

The basis of ST is the development of a whole set of skills: orienteering (using a map, compass, GPS-navigators), cross-country techniques (hiking, mountain hiking, water hiking, speleotourism, etc.), first aid, knowledge of the basics of survival in extreme conditions, and, of course, excellent physical fitness, allowing to overcome significant loads and difficult natural terrain - from mountain passes and rough rivers to impassable forests and canyons.

For example, in Russia, sports tourism has a rich history, and its development is closely connected with the formation of the national system of physical culture and sports. The first tourist hikes appeared in the early XX century, and by the middle of the century, the main routes, and categories of complexity were formed. Modern sports tourism is classified by types of tourist activity (hiking, water, mountain, skiing, cycling, and many others), by the level of complexity of routes (from simple to extremely complex), and by the type of organization of hikes (from individual to group). Classification of the complexity of routes considers such parameters as the length of the route, altitude difference, technical complexity of the obstacles overcome, climatic conditions and the presence of potential hazards (<https://wwbmstu.ru>).

The key feature of sports tourism is its amateurism. This means that tourists plan and organize their own hikes, are responsible for their own safety, and overcome difficulties together. Self-activity, in this context, is not just the absence of organized accompaniment of guides, but the manifestation of initiative, independence, responsibility and collectivism. It builds valuable personal qualities such as perseverance, determination, teamwork, the ability to make decisions in non-standard situations and adapt to changing conditions. Self-activity in sports tourism allows you to maximize the potential of the individual, realize yourself, get a unique experience and deep satisfaction from the achievement of the goal.

However, modern sports tourism is developing in two main directions, often complementing rather than excluding each other. The first is commercial organized tourism, where travel companies offer ready-made tours with experienced guides, providing safety and comfort. Tourists receive a full package of services, including transfer, accommodation, meals, an escort, and equipment rental. This is a convenient option for beginners who do not have enough experience or time to organize treks on their own.

The second direction is the development of organized amateur sports tourism, where tourists themselves plan the route, buy equipment, coordinate their actions and are responsible for the safety of the hike. However, this does not exclude organizational work: groups are often registered in special federations or tourist clubs, undergo training and certification, plan hikes collectively, and can receive advice from experienced athletes. This approach combines autonomy and safety, maximizing the effectiveness of learning and fun. In addition, sports, and recreational tourism is also developing, focused not only on athletic performance, but also on restoring health and relaxation in nature. It may include hiking, cycling, horseback riding, yoga tours, and other active activities, considering the individual physical capabilities of the participants.

Above all, positive changes affect labor markets. In particular, new jobs are created in many sectors of the economy, the tourism balance and many other micro-environmental indicators improve. We will look at the mechanisms of sport's impact on a country or region that regularly holds certain sporting events:

1. **Regional system.** Undoubtedly, the public of fans, athletes, and coaches must migrate to the place where the competition will occur. The function of transporting people to the destination is carried out by the transportation system. Thus, fans, athletes, coaches, sports journalists, and commentators will for a while become passengers for sea, river, air, rail and road transportation. By meeting the transportation of passengers, the transportation system benefits from ticket sales in return. Colonga profits pay taxes, which will complete local budgets and allow officials to improve the welfare of the people living in the region.

In addition, by creating demand for transportation, sports tourism will serve as the basis for job creation - new routes are created, transportation Toki is growing, and new station complexes are being built. Increased demand for labor leads to increased wages in the area.

Two. **Hospitality Business...** Athletes and fans who have reached the competition must stop to live anywhere at some point. Temporary accommodation services are provided by the hospitality industry which includes hotels with various services and facilities, engines, camps, and tourist bases. The demand for the hotel complex by fans and athletes will eventually bring money for hotel services because the tourist is a tourist region, tourist, tourist, tourism, tours, excursions, and cultural vacations. Naturally, they spend money in the region for all these events.

3. **Sports facilities.** Modern major competitions (championships, cup meetings, fields days, Olympics) cannot be imagined without appropriate, specially designed and built sports facilities - stadiums, swimming pools, bicycle paths, driving ranges, ski tracks, gyms, and other components of sports infrastructure. The newest sports facilities of this type are technically complex conglomerates. Their creation requires large expenditures of intellectual labor and capital. This circumstance directly affects the market value of sports facilities - the price of modern sports complexes and facilities is tens and hundreds of thousands of dollars, and the cost of large facilities can reach tens of millions of dollars. Nevertheless, the benefits of implementing such investments are usually several times greater than the costs.

In addition, the benefits obtained are two different functions: Firstly, the investment in sports facilities will be profitable and paid for in the next 4-5 years; secondly, they are minor, in the time interval between major competitions strengthen their moral and physical education and as a result increase productivity and improve the welfare of the citizens of this area [six]. Besides the aforementioned economic spheres, sports tours also have beneficial effects on other sectors of the economic complex. In particular, tourists were memorable gifts, food, excursions, entertainment Demand leads to significant development of trade and service business, settlement, and banking sector, advertising business and catering business in advertising business and catering business. Undoubtedly, all demand is reflected in new jobs and wage growth.

For example, the total amount of direct income from the World Cup, accompanied by an unprecedented influx of foreign fans, supposedly reached \$14 billion, ITAR-TASS reported, citing South Korean Deputy Prime Minister Chung Yong-Cher. However, in reality, the official emphasized, the total economic effect is much higher, as "this figure does not reflect indirect profits." The net profit and the global 10 stadiums have created 500,000 jobs. In addition, the process of job creation comes with a "multiplier effect" that investing in one area of the economy will lead to employment not only in it, but also in other sectors of the economy and increased income [11]. For example, athletes, coaches, fans, journalists and commentators demand food. Buy these products, They create demand for agricultural products, and agriculture is already developing development.

It should be noted that in the process of foreign travel, people get acquainted with the culture, customs, and mentality of other peoples, establish personal contacts with each other and begin to understand each other better. Of course, sports tourism sometimes includes some negative manifestations - for example, clashes of fans of different teams or hooliganism of supporters of losing athletes. However, all these negative phenomena cannot cast doubt on the various advantages of sports tourism. The development of sports tourism in Uzbekistan has important prospects that can be realized through integrated approaches to infrastructure, marketing, and

education, and strategic investment. Further efforts to strengthen cooperation between states, the private sector, and international partners will contribute to the sustainable growth of domestic sports tourism.

Conclusion

We would like to note that there is significant potential for the development of sports tourism in Uzbekistan and that an integrated approach can be considered. The importance of tourism for both the country and the world cannot be overemphasized. Its development continues to grow: the quality of service for tourists is improving, attention to the preservation of nature and ecology is increasing, and cultural and aesthetic norms are being observed. The quality of medical services is improving and a wide range of entertainment activities such as excursions, festivals and sporting events are becoming available. All these factors certainly have a positive impact on the tourism industry in the country, contributing to economic growth, job creation, and strengthening cultural ties. Moreover, tourism development contributes to the improvement of the living standards of the local population, as the influx of tourists stimulates entrepreneurial activity and develops infrastructure.

Improved infrastructure, training of skilled personnel, and aggressive international promotion allow the country to occupy a valuable space in the sports and tourism market. This not only increases the flow of tourists but also contributes to the economic growth of the region. With the right strategy to improve infrastructure and train professionals, the country can attract more tourists and strengthen its position in the international sector.

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